

Synthesis of Substituted 1,3,5-Triazines as Tuberculostatic Agents

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A series of 2,4-diarylamino-6-(pyridine-4-carboxhydrazido/substituted benzhydrazido)-1,3,5-triazines have been synthesised and tested against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strain H₃₇R_v. Some of them have shown significant tuberculostatic activity.

THERAPEUTIC significance of isonicotinic acid hydrazide and analogous hydrazine derivatives as tuberculostatic agents stimulated research in the field of chemotherapy of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. A number of compounds of this category have been synthesised and tested for various therapeutic implications¹⁻¹⁴. Some S-triazine derivatives have been shown to possess remarkable tuberculostatic activity¹⁰⁻¹². This prompted us to synthesise some new substituted 1,3,5-triazines and screen them for antimycobacterial activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography. The infrared spectra were recorded in KBr phase using Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. The structures of the compounds have been established on the basis of their elemental analysis, counter synthesis, mixed melting point and infrared spectrum. The ir spectra of these compounds show characteristic absorption bands at 3400-3100 cm⁻¹ (-NH) and 1705-1690 cm⁻¹ (-CONH-).

Preparation of hydrazides :

The substituted benzhydrazides, having hydrogen, 4-chloro, 4-nitro, 4-hydroxy and isonicotinic acid hydrazide as substituents, have been prepared according to literature method¹⁵⁻¹⁹. 2-Arylamino-4,6-dichloro-1,3,5-triazines (I) have been synthesised in the usual manner.

2,4-Diarylamino-6-chloro-1,3,5-triazine (II) : These were prepared by the various methods reported in literature^{21,22}.

2-Arylamino-4-chloro-6-(pyridine-4-carboxhydrazido)-1,3,5-triazine (III) : Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (0.01 mole) and 2-arylamino-4,6-dichloro-1,3,5-triazine (0.01 mole) were dissolved in dioxane and the solution stirred at 30-35° for 3 hr with the simultaneous dropwise addition of aqueous NaHCO₃ (1 M; 10 ml). The contents were cooled and poured into cold water and acidified (5 M HCl) to

congo red. The product so obtained was filtered, washed with water followed by cold EtOH, dried and crystallised from EtOH (95%).

Five new 2-arylamino-4-chloro-6-(pyridine-4-carboxhydrazido)-1,3,5-triazines have been thus prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Ar	m.p. °C	Yield %	Activity*
1.	Phenyl	188	91.2	+
2.	<i>o</i> -Cl-Phenyl	240	93.8	+
3.	<i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl	255	89.8	+
4.	<i>p</i> -Phenitlyl	158	93.0	+
5.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	250	85.2	+

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analysis.
+ = Tuberculostatic at 25 µg/ml.

Preparation of 2,4-diarylamino-6-benzhydrazido-1,3,5-triazines (IV) : Benzhydrazide (0.01 mole) and II (0.01 mole) were dissolved in dioxane and the solution refluxed for 3 hr with the simultaneous dropwise addition of aqueous Na₂CO₃ (1 M; 10 ml). The reaction mixture after cooling was poured into cold water, filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol (95%).

Similarly, condensation of substituted benzhydrazide/isonicotinic acid hydrazide with II and arylamines with III furnished 2,4-diarylamino-6-[pyridine-4-carboxhydrazido/substituted benzhydrazido]-1,3,5-triazines in 75 to 88% yield.

Twenty such compounds have been synthesised (Table 2).

Biological screening :

The *in vitro* antibacterial activity of the synthesised compounds were studied at 25, 50, 100 and 200 µg/ml (solvent-ethanol) against H₃₇R_v strain of

Mycobacterium tuberculosis using Lowenstein-Jensen egg medium. The retardation of the growth rate was studied upto six weeks at 37°. The procedure was duplicated using only solvent for control purposes (Table 2).

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	Ar	Ar'	m.p. °C	Yield %	Activity
1.	Phenyl	Phenyl	221-22	88.2	-
2.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	270(d)	88.5	-
3.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	317-18	80.1	-
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Isonicotinyl	322	92.6	+
5.*	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	250-51(d)	86.2	-
6.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	Phenyl	300(d)	88.8	-
7.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	280	83.9	-
8.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	202	74.8	-
9.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	Phenyl	240	86.1	-
10.*	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	181-82	74.1	-
11.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	328	83.2	-
12.*	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	168(d)	72.5	-
13.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	4-Pyridyl	99-100	90.3	-
14.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Phenyl	320(d)	88.2	-
15.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	300(d)	83.2	-
16.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	307(d)	72.1	-
17.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	189	73.5	-
18.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Phenyl	280	79.6	-
19.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	260(d)	71.8	-
20.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	240-41	78.2	-
21.	Phenyl	4-Pyridyl	260	94.1	+
22.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	4-Pyridyl	288	91.2	+
23.*	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	277	81.1	-
24.*	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	312	73.6	-
25.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	4-Pyridyl	296	90.2	+

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analysis.

+ = Tuberculostatic at 25 µg/ml.

- = Inactive against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* at 200 µg/ml.

* Solvent - acetone.

Results and Discussion

The results of the *in vitro* antimycobacterial study show that ten compounds are active at 25 µg/ml and the remaining compounds fail to inhibit the growth of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. All the active compounds, i.e. No. 1 to 5 (Table 1) and No. 4, 13, 21, 22, and 25 (Table 2) have isonicotinyl hydrazine moiety. The presence of benzhydrazone/substituted benzhydrazide or arylamine moiety in compounds (III and IV) have not exhibited any tuberculostatic activity. Therefore, the only conclusion that can be drawn from these results is that the isonicotinyl hydrazine moiety is responsible for activity in the compounds.

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References

- H. H. FOX and G. T. GIBAS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, **18**, 994; 1955, **20**, 60; 1956, **21**, 256.
- I. L. DASCENSIO, E. TITSWORTH, E. GRUNBERG, R. J. SCHNITZER and B. LEIWANT, *Quart. Bull. Sea View Hosp.*, 1952, **13**, 3.
- J. BERNSTEIN, W. P. JAMBOR, W. A. LOTT, F. PANSY, B. A. STEINBERG and H. L. YALE, *Amer. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1953, **67**, 354.
- R. BONICKE and J. KRACHT, *Z. Hyg. Infektionskrankh.*, 1954, **139**, 140.
- H. A. OFFE, G. DOMAGK and W. SIEPKEN, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1952, **7**, 446.
- M. CLAESSEN, P. VAN DIJCK and H. VANDERHAEGHE, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1954, **6**, 127.
- S. KAKIMOTO, E. K. THIEMER and E. WEMPE, *Arseneimittel-Forsch.*, 1960, **10**, 963.
- E. FOURNIER and L. PETIT, *Therapie*, 1966, **21**, 787.
- N. B. MAHISHI, B. H. IYER and M. SIRISI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 67.
- N. A. LANGALIA and K. A. THAKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 89; 1982, **59**, 1099.
- H. K. SHUKLA, N. A. LANGALIA, N. C. DESAI and K. A. THAKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 1101.
- H. K. SHUKLA, N. C. DESAI, N. A. LANGALIA and K. A. THAKER, *J. Inst. Chemists (India)*, 1982, **54**, 130.
- H. H. FOX in "Medicinal Chemistry", (Ed.) A. BURGER, Interscience, 1960, p. 982.
- C. KAISER and C. L. ZIRKLE in "Medicinal Chemistry", (Ed.) A. BURGER, Interscience, 1970, p. 1483.
- STOLLE, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1904, **69**, 145.
- SHIH SAH, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1935, **1**, 56.
- O. TRACHMANN, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1895, **51**, 168.
- P. T. SAH and K. H. YUIN, *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **13**, 77.
- G. DOMAGK, H. A. OFFE and W. SIEPKEN, *Deutsche Med. Wchnschr.*, 1952, **77**, 573.
- C. N. WOLF, *U. S. Patent*, 2720480; *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, **50**, 13101.
- M. GOI, *Yuki Gosei Kagaku Kyokai Sh.*, 1960, **18**, 327 *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, **54**, 19702.
- N. V. KOZIOVA, *Z. Obh. Sch. Khim.*, 1963, **30**, 3303; *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, **54**, 19702.